

MARKETING OF SOCIAL SERVICES IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM

Definition of the essence of marketing in the field of

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Abstract. *Social media marketing is used for all traditional marketing purposes - to attract customers.*

Keyword: *social media platforms are suitable for business. This does not mean that your small business should start using some.*

Marketing includes a wide variety of activities, including marketing research, product development, sales organization, pricing, and advertising. Social service marketing is a type of human activity aimed at satisfying needs through exchange. The scope of social services marketing has recently expanded to include, in addition to goods, services, organizations, places, and ideas.

Thus, the concept of service marketing appeared, which implies the process of developing, promoting and implementing services, focused on identifying special customer needs and designed to help customers evaluate the services of a service organization and make the right choice. Having originated in the manufacturing sector, the marketing of social services for a long time did not find appropriate application in the service sector and, in particular, in the tourism sector. However, the increasing competition and commercialization of tourism activities have led to the need for the early introduction of the basic elements of social services marketing into the practice of a tourist enterprise. At the same time, tourism has certain features related to the nature of social services, forms of sales, and so on. Thus, in order to ensure an effective technology for selling tourist products, preliminary work is needed, during which a set of services is prepared at a fixed price, and the real demand for it manifests itself much later. The management of the travel agency must guess the wishes of the buyers, make a choice for them of the direction of travel, accommodation facilities, mode of transport, etc. and only after that offer a ready-made package for sale. Based on this feature of the production of tourist products and its sale, the key cheaper ones, etc. So, in order to really use social services marketing as a reliable tool for achieving success in the market, specialists of tourism enterprises need to master its methodology and the ability to apply them depending on the specific situation. Thus, marketing of social services in tourism is a system of continuous coordination of the services offered with services that are in demand in the market and that a travel company is able to offer profitably for itself and more effectively than competitors do. The essence of social services marketing is to ensure that the offers of tourist services are necessarily oriented towards the consumer and to constantly align the capabilities of the enterprise with the requirements of the market. The purpose of marketing social services in tourism is to systematically determine the range of data required in connection with the marketing situation in which the travel company is located, data collection, analysis, and a report on the results. Marketing of social services in the field of tourism is applied both at the macro and micro levels. In particular, at the macro level, the scale of marketing activities within administrative structures is determined by the degree of impact of tourism on the country's economy and government policy on tourism.

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For example, in the United States, as part of the Office of Travel and Tourism, responsible for the development of public policy in the field of tourism, there is a tourism marketing bureau.

The main objectives of its activities are the development and implementation of programs in the field of tourism development, coordination of projects and programs in the field of marketing, taking into account American and international tourism projects, stimulating consumer demand for tourist trips to the United States, etc. At the micro level, there are organizational structures within a separate travel company (departments, departments) that deal exclusively with marketing, as well as independent marketing companies that work to order. There are several main groups of customers who are most interested in conducting marketing research in tourism. Firstly, these are national representative offices of foreign countries, national tourism organizations, whose tasks include both tracking the level of interest in their countries from domestic tourists and travel agencies, and finding ways to effectively promote their destinations in the domestic market. Secondly, these are the most active tour operators who strive not only to maintain their already won positions, but also to find new business development directions for themselves. Thirdly, these are organizations and firms whose work is closely related to tourism (advertising, legal, information). For the first and third

However, the need for this kind of market research is rather episodic, because they are less dependent on current fluctuations and changes in the tourism market. As for tour operators, their dependence on market conditions is large and constant, therefore, a serious attitude to marketing research is a kind of indicator of the future work of a tour operator, the basis for their further success.

For tour operators, the most typical topics of marketing research are: o compiling ratings of the popularity of tourist destinations among tourists and travel agencies. When building various kinds of ratings, the correctness and unambiguity of the calculation methodology, determining the degree of influence of individual performance indicators of travel agencies on the resulting rating indicator are very important; o assessment of the situation according to the direction presented on the market, but new for a particular tour operator. First of all, it is of interest to identify the real picture of the presence of leading tour operators on the market (who already have significant experience working with the destination), to assess the possibility of a certain redistribution of the market in terms of attracting some tourists and travel agencies;

o assessment of the current and prospective market situation in fundamentally new tourist destinations. It is about developing and introducing new destinations for tourists to the market, assessing the volume of the potential market, studying the current level of interest and attitude of potential tourists to new programs; o assessment of promising market development opportunities in certain areas. An important point here is to identify opportunities and ways to further develop and promote a particular destination, identify the attitude of tourists to the level of current offers, calculate the return rate in this area and make possible changes to existing programs in order to maintain consumer interest in them;

o evaluation of the effectiveness of advertising. In this research segment, the analysis of the general advertising campaign of the tour operator is carried out both as a whole (the formation of a positive image of the company among tourists and travel agencies) and individual parameters; o evaluation of the effectiveness of mass media for advertisers.

We are talking about choosing a list of printed publications and media channels, studying and determining the ways consumers actually use to find the information they need about offers, as

well as identifying forms of work with printed thematic travel publications, the frequency and depth of work with them, and so on.;

o analysis of the quality of the tourist product. This area of work provides for the creation of a system of ongoing quality control of tourist products offered by the operator, identification of negative aspects in the organization of recreation and excursion programs (including, from the point of view of the host party, providing tourists with the necessary information and the level of work of managers); o analysis of problematic situations. In this part of the research, almost any issues related to the lack of sufficient information from the tour operator can be considered, which do not allow us to get a complete picture of the causes of the problem and its true extent. In this case, the tasks of the marketing research contractor may include work on concretizing the problem posed or transferring it to a higher level in order to obtain the most objective picture and identify the underlying causes of this problem. The essential point in this case is the development of a research methodology, which should. Such an idea of the directions of marketing work in tourism comes out of the current situation in the tourism services market, especially in organized tourism, where tours in the form of pre-planned and completed packages consisting of several services are sold to agents at set prices long before their actual sale to the end consumer. Thus, marketing in the field of tourism is the mechanism that ensures the connection of intra-company management with the realities of the external environment. He provides information about market conditions, about competitors operating in the market, about trends and the direction of tourist flows, the transformation of a tourist product, about trends in changing tastes and preferences of consumers and in the form of marketing strategies, plans, recommendations, promotions and other tools, affects all elements of the management of a travel company, taking a direct part in the company's production activities. Moreover, it is the marketing of social services that is behind.

References

1. Базарова, М. С., Шарипова, М., & Нуруллоев, О. (2021). “РАҚАМЛИ ИҚТИСОДИЁТ” ДА АҲОЛИНИНГ ИШ БИЛАН БАНДЛИГИ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ. *САМАРҚАНД ДАВЛАТ УНИВЕРСИТЕТИ*, 482.
2. Supiyevna, B. M. (2024). O'ZBEKISTONDAGI XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA AHOLINI ISH BILAN BAND ETISH YO'LLARI. *Scientific Journal of Actuarial Finance and Accounting*, 4(08), 78-84.
3. Bazarova, M. (2025). STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT IN THE SYSTEM STRATEGIC MARKETING. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence*, 1(4), 1707-1710.
4. Bazarova, M. (2025). O'ZBEKISTONDA TURIZM SOHASIDA MARKETING STRATEGIYALARINI KOMPLEKSINING XUSUSIYATLARI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(6), 483-486.
5. Bazarova, M. (2025). MECHANISMS, METHODS AND TRENDS OF IMPLEMENTING MANAGEMENT MODELS IN MODERN MANAGEMENT EDUCATION. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence*, 1(1), 591-597.
6. Bazarova, M. (2025). KADRLAR SIFATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO 'NALISHLARI VA ISTIQBOLLARI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(4), 571-577.
7. Bazarova, M. (2025). THE ROLE OF THE ECONOMY IN THE EFFICIENT USE OF TOURISM FACILITIES. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(4), 629-634.

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8. Bazarova, M. (2025). STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT IN THE SYSTEM STRATEGIC MARKETING. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence*, 1(4), 1707-1710.
9. Supiyevna, B. M. (2025). KICHIK BIZNESNI MOLIYAVIY QO 'LLAB-QUVVATLASHDA BANK KREDITINING XORIJIY TAJRIBASI. YANGI O 'ZBEKISTON, YANGI TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI, 2(9), 715-721.
10. Bazarova, M. S., & Mahmudov, Z. (2025). SANOAT KORXONALARIDA INVESTITSIYANI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(5), 668-674.
11. Bazarova, M. S. (2022). FACTORS THAT ENSURE THE SUCCESSFUL IMPLEMENTATION OF A SYSTEM OF KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS IN THE.
12. Bazarova, M. (2025). O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA DAVLAT MOLIYASI TIZIMIDAGI ISLOHOTLARNING ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 29-36.
13. Bazarova, M. (2025). DIRECTIONS FOR FINANCING AND IMPROVING SMALL BUSINESSES IN UZBEKISTAN. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence*, 1(2), 283-286.
14. Bazarova, M. (2025). O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA DAVLAT MOLIYASI TIZIMIDAGI ISLOHOTLARNING ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 29-36.
15. Supiyevna, B. M. (2025). THE US TAXES ON INCOME. *MODERN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM AND INNOVATIVE TEACHING SOLUTIONS*, 1(7), 221-226.
16. Шадиев, А. Х. (2025). СТРАТЕГИИ РЕГИОНАЛЬНОГО СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ. YANGI O 'ZBEKISTON, YANGI TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI, 2(9), 708-714.
17. Шадиев, А. Х. (2025). МЕТОДОЛОГИЯ АНАЛИЗА СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ РЕГИОНА. *IZLANUVCHI*, 1(6), 420-426.
18. Shadiyev, A. X. (2025). BUXORO VILOYATI IJTIMOY-IQTISODIY KO'RSATKICHLARI TAHLILI. *TA'LIM, TARBIYA VA INNOVATSIYALAR JURNALI*, 1(6), 225-230.
19. Shadiev, A. K. (2025). WAYS OF SUSTAINABLE SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF REGIONS BASED ON ADVANCED FOREIGN EXPERIENCE. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 5(6), 1967-1973.
20. Shadiev, A. K. (2025). Regional development modern concepts: theoretical approaches and scientific basis. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 5(6), 1974-1979.

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